

Protest Codebook Supplement: Guide for Human Coding of University Responses and Police Actions Text

Higher Ed Protest Event Dataset (HiPED) Project

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NOTE TO EXTERNAL READERS

This version of the project's *Codebook Supplement* has been modified slightly to include explanatory notes and formatting changes; however, the content is the same as the original document which research assistants referred to as they coded the university responses and police actions text.

Footnotes that come from the original document are noted as such; all other footnotes are explanatory for external readers. Hyperlinks to internal project documents were removed, but noted.

INTRODUCTION

The intention of this research project is to **create event data on university and college (higher education) protests in Canada and the United States, including university responses to those protests and protest policing, between 2012 and 2018**. We have a special analytic interest in anti-racism protest, but we are studying higher education protest on a wide range of issues, from fossil fuel divestment to labour protections to White supremacy. Our ultimate goal is to understand large-scale patterns in student and campus protest movements and universities' management of protests.

To understand those patterns, we are creating the Student & Campus Protest Events Dataset. Constructing the dataset involves using computational text analysis and then sociological hand-coding of all student and campus protests reported in student newspapers. Research assistants on the team do the hand-coding: they identify and mark protest-related information within newspaper articles using an online interface. In each article, coders determine if the article included information about a protest event that meets our criteria for a higher education protest. If the article does, coders identify specific characteristics of the protest such as location, duration, form, and issue. This process is aided by the Machine-learning Protest Event Data System (MPEDS), a system for generating protest event data using tools from natural language processing and statistics. Ellen Berrey oversees the work of hand-coding, Alex Hanna created and oversees MPEDS.

The purpose of this Codebook Supplement is to provide instructions for doing the hand-coding of a subset of the existing protest event codings. Specifically, it explains how to standardize the text selected for University Responses and Police Actions, in order to convert that data from qualitative text into standardized categories. We refer to this as the "Codebook Supplement" to differentiate it from the Protest Codebook, which our RA team used to code the data on the protests, including where and when the protest happened, the issues involved, the forms (types of actions) protestors took, the newspaper text on any university responses and/or police actions, and more.

STANDARDIZING UNIVERSITY RESPONSES & POLICE ACTIONS

The initial hand-coding of newspaper articles has already been done by Coders. The coding includes different question formats, depending on the data:

- Checkboxes, i.e. standardized categories
- Text fields in which Coders wrote in answers (e.g., Article Description, Event Description, start date, location),
- Text select- to copy and capture chunks of relevant text/words in the article.

The text select includes any text in the newspaper article about university responses to the protest event and any text on police actions around that protest event.

For this stage of the research, we created new protocols for standardizing the University Responses and Police Actions text select. Using these protocol will enable us to analyze the data quantitatively, e.g. to compare how protests based on racial issues were policed in contrast to protests based on non-racial issues, such as labour strikes.

Your Task as Coding University Responses

Your role is to learn the protocol for coding University Responses that is detailed below, and then to apply the protocol to pre-selected text on University Responses in order to “hand-code” the data. The hand-coding is, essentially, turning qualitative text into standardized categories (i.e., checkboxes). You also will be asked to provide input into the protocol itself, as we continue to refine and improve it.

You also will be given access to a Google spreadsheet with that University Responses Data you need to code and you will be trained on how to use the MPEDS system to do the hand-coding.

Finally, you will record some details of work in your own internal timesheet, including your hours worked and the Event IDs that you coded.

How To Use This Codebook Supplement

This Codebook Supplement provides instructions on using the University Responses protocol. Please disregard any instructions below regarding Police Actions coding.

This Codebook Supplement provides criteria to help you make decisions as you code the text selected for University Responses and Police Actions. ***Understanding the Codebook Supplement is***

essential to coding the data accurately. Please read it carefully and become familiar with all of the definitions, procedures, and notes.

Keep this Codebook Supplement open whenever you are coding. **While coding, you will be going back and forth between the Codebook Supplement, the spreadsheet with University Responses data, and MPEDS repeatedly.**

If you have any questions or challenges during the process of hand-coding, make a note of these and share them with the project manager and/or broader team.

Note that in this mini-codebook, for brevity, we refer to “universities” instead of referring to both “universities and colleges,” although the study examines both universities and colleges.¹

ENTERING ALREADY CODED DATA

Your first task working with the data will be to enter University Responses codings that were completed by other RAs previously but that have not yet been entered into MPEDS. This will give you an opportunity to get familiar with the MPEDS interface before learning the codes and definitions. Use this [*TO ENTER Univ Responses Codings*](#)² spreadsheet (Data to Enter tab) to access the data to enter, then follow the instructions on MPEDS below.

MPEDS

Accessing MPEDS

The MPEDS Annotation Interface is the online interface that Alex Hanna designed for this project. This is the technology you will use to access articles and code and enter data. Each individual has a unique username and password for accessing MPEDS, in your internal timesheet (e.g., UR_Moneet).

- 1) **Open Mozilla Firefox** (DO NOT USE Safari or Google Chrome. These browsers are not compatible with the system)

¹ Original Footnote: If you're wondering why: In the U.S., the terms “university” and “college” are often used interchangeably. That said, U.S. universities typically award 4-year undergraduate degrees and also have graduate programs. Colleges, in contrast, typically award 4-year undergraduate degrees (different than colleges in Canada), but some college programs might be shorter, e.g. for a technical degree (more like colleges in Canada).

² Internal document.

2) **Enter (and bookmark) the website URL:**

http://sheriff.ssc.wisc.edu/campus_protest/event_creator/

3) **When prompted, enter your username and password**

Upon entering the system, **ensure that the system displays your name**. Otherwise you will not be able to receive credit for your work. You will see two ways to access the same articles: The Event Coder Interface and List.

4) **Select Event Coder Interface**

This is where you will access articles and events. You should copy and paste the Article ID from the TEXT sheet into the URL. The example below is Article 2398.

sheriff.ssc.wisc.edu/campus_protest/event_creator/ARTICLENUMBER

In the Event Coder Interface for each individual article, there are three panels:

The Article: The panel on the left side of the screen contains the article to be analyzed. This is the article you will use to code information. There is a scroll bar that will allow you to view the entire article. You will be using the article text minimally.

Event Descriptions: The middle panel will eventually contain some very brief text once you save your coding (the Original Event ID + UR).

The Coding Panel: When you **click on “Add event +”** on the panel on the right side of the screen, this will open the coding pane. Notice there are five tabs within the coding pane. More on that below.

MPEDS Event Creator - Campus Protests Home Logged in as Ellen Logout

Students, members of Williamsburg community conduct protest following Darren Wilson decision

Flat Hat: College of William and Mary | NEWS; Pg. 1 | Amanda Williams | 2014-12-01 | Flat Hat: College of William and Mary_2014-12-01_21

A group in Williamsburg took part in a nationwide event Nov. 25, hosting a Black Lives Matter Protest.

After several speakers addressed those gathered, the march began in front of the College of William and Mary bookstore, traveled down Richmond Road, passed the Sadler center and ended at the Sir Christopher Wren Building.

Travis Harris, a first year American studies Ph.D candidate, opened the protest with 4 minutes and 30 seconds of silence, in solidarity with protests around the country, to commemorate the 4 hours and 30 minutes that Michael Brown, fatally shot by an officer earlier this year, lay in the street. Harris organized the entire event with a future event in mind, tentatively planned for the spring.

"My goal is to have a candid conversation on race here in Williamsburg," Harris said. "My hope is that by having this conversation, each side is going to understand each other better. My end goal is racial reconciliation and peace."

The countrywide protest movement was sparked by the Nov. 24 St. Louis grand jury decision not to indict Darren Wilson, the white police officer who shot Brown, an unarmed, 18-year-old black male. The shooting occurred Aug. 9 in Ferguson, Mo., a suburb of St. Louis. The Williamsburg protest was just one of hundreds from New York to Los Angeles, and stayed peaceful, unlike some others.

Pat Griffith (left) from Williamsburg (with Dr. Marshall Barrv '61) said he was at the protest

Event descriptions

Add event +

Basic Info
Yes/No Text Select Preset

Provide a short description of this article.

Provide a short description of this event.

Start date

End date

Location (City, State/Province, Country)

Save

Mark Done and Go to Next »

Coding with MPEDS

Within MPEDS, you will create a “University Responses coding” for each Original Event ID assigned to you. Initially, you will do this using the [TO ENTER Univ Responses Codings](#)³ spreadsheet (Data to Enter tab); you can enter that data without knowing the protocol. Later you will use the [TO CODE Univ Responses Data](#)⁴ spreadsheet to do the coding. Follow these steps:

- 5) For each Original Event ID: Click on “Add event +”. The Coding pane will become visible. You will be adding information to four of those tabs: Basic Info, Preset, Text Select, Preset 2 (not the Yes/No tab). However, you will not be adding information to all the fields in those four tabs; you will only fill in information specifically relevant for University Responses coding, in this order.

Note: Your University Responses coding will be assigned its own new Event ID, which you will be able to see in the Event descriptions pane. However, you do not need to keep track of that new Event ID.

a) Basic Info - Fill in these four fields:

- i) **Event Description (“Provide a short description of event”):**
Copy the Original Event ID from the spreadsheet and paste it into MPEDS in the Event Description with the words “OEID”. Also in the Event Description,

³ Internal document.

⁴ Internal document.

type UNIV. For example:

OEID 1444 UNI

ii) **Start date, End date, Location:**

Copy the start date, end date, and location for this Original Event ID from the Data spreadsheet and paste those into MPEDS in the relevant fields.

Standard format for location: City, Two Letter State/Province Code, USA/Canada. Examples:

- Waterloo, ON, Canada
- Los Angeles, CA, USA

Please correct the location text if there is a misspelling or if the text does not match the standard format. Search online for the State/Province Code if you need to fix it, to ensure it is correct.

b) Preset

i) **Forms:**

Check off the Forms() that are listed for this Original Event ID in the Data spreadsheet. Please don't skip any!

c) Preset 2

Code university responses, using the protocol below! Refer to the text selects in the Data spreadsheet and consult the Event Description to determine the codes that apply. Select those in the interface.

Again, when working with the TO ENTER codings, you won't need to know the protocol because you'll be entering codings already completed. So just select the relevant categories from the list. Please don't skip any!

d) Text Select

In the Text Select tab, scroll down to "University Responses+". Using the Data spreadsheet, select each of the text selects within the text of the article and, for each selection, click that + symbol next to University responses. This can be done by copying each chunk of text, or just the first few words, in each row in the Data spreadsheet for that Original Event ID and then searching for it in the article text displayed in MPEDS.

If any of the text selects are repetitive or not codeable, you do not need to select those.

- e) **Basic Info - Click “Save.”**
This step is mostly procedural. If you accidentally close the browser while coding, don't worry. **The interface saves all the recorded information automatically.**
- 6) **In the Assignments tab of the Data sheet:** For that Original Event ID, record your initials and the date you coded the event.
- 7) **If that same Article ID has more than one Original Event ID associated with it:** Either now or later (if it is assigned to you), you may need to add additional event(s) to the same article using the same process. You will follow the same steps as above for the additional event(s). Once you have done this, you will see, in the Event description pane for the article, all the “Event descriptions” associated with that article.
- 8) **To continue coding:** In MPEDS, enter the next Article ID assigned to you into the URL, then start at Step 5.

To Edit or Delete Your Prior Coding

If you ever need to edit or delete your coding, enter the Article ID in the URL. You will see that the box in the middle panel for “Event descriptions” will contain the text that you added there (the Original Event ID + UNIV). **Select the pencil icon to edit** your University Responses coding. **Select the trash can to delete** that coding.

THE UNIVERSITY RESPONSES TEXT TO CODE

To access text to code and other relevant information, you will use the *TO CODE University Responses Data spreadsheet*⁵ (i.e. the “Data spreadsheet”). The sheet has two main tabs: Data to Code and Assignments.

The Data to Code tab contains the data you will be working with. For each protest event you are coding, text already has been selected for University Responses. You will access the text selected in this spreadsheet tab every time you code. Again, ***while coding, you will constantly be going back and forth between this data spreadsheet, MPEDS, and this Codebook Supplement.***

Within the tab, you will see a column with Article IDs and a column with Original Event IDs. Each Original Event ID refers to a protest event. Most articles report on one event, so they have one Original Event ID. If the same Article ID is associated with more than one Original Event ID, that means the article reported on multiple protests.

For each Event ID, you will see University Responses text; this is the information you'll be coding. You will also see identifying information about the protest, including the location, start date, and

⁵ Internal document.

event description. For each Event ID, every “chunk” of University Responses text selected is on a different row - that is because the text came from different parts of the article.

The Assignments tab is for record-keeping. It lists the Original Event IDs you should code and has a place to record your name next to the events you coded as well as any questions and responses. We will use this tab to communicate with each other about your specific questions about coding. Whenever you have a question, shade the appropriate cell in **bright blue**. Ellen or another student will review and answer your question; they will undo your shading and add their own bright blue shading to their response. Once you have resolved the question and have made any necessary changes to your coding, please make sure there is no bright blue shading left in the row. In other words, bright blue is an indication that we have unresolved questions concerning the coding for a specific event.

How To Compare Your Coding with Your Partner’s and Create the Final Coding

Whenever you need to review and compare your coding with your partner’s, you can use the dashboard that Alex created. In Firefox, open:

<https://alexhanna.shinyapps.io/event-dashboard/>

In the left side bar, select Coder Comparison and enter the article ID. Just focus on the University Responses codings done by you and your partner. Ignore the original codings of the article (you can hide them if you prefer, by selecting only your coder ID and your partner’s to display).

With your partner, decide which coding you will keep. If the “best” coding needs corrections, the person who did that coding should make those corrections in MPEDS. The other person should go into MPEDS, enter the Article ID in the URL, and select the trash can for that coding :(In the Data spreadsheet, bold the name of the person whose coding you used.

What To Do When an Article Has Been Double Coded

Sometimes an article has been double-coded - meaning, the same article was coded by more than one RA. You can tell if an article has been double coded because the coding is shaded in light yellow in the Assignments tab. You also can tell because the same article number will be associated with two different Event IDs and different Coders’ names. For example:

Article 122, Event 555, Sara

Article 122, Event 71, Tsitsi

You should code both versions (both events) in MPEDS. Later, when the Feedback sheet is set up, you should compare your codings.

- 1) First compare your coding of one event (e.g., Event 555, Sara - Arrest, Weapons, Instruct) with the other coder you are paired with and create a FINAL row.
- 2) Then compare your coding of the other event (e.g. Event 71, Tsitsi - Arrest, Weapons) with the other coder you are paired with and create a FINAL row.
- 3) Then, compare those two FINAL rows:
 - a) If the codings are identical, you should select one to make the FINAL (choose the one with the most text select if you can't decide). For the other one, shade it in gray.
 - b) If your two FINAL codings differ in any way (e.g., 71 doesn't include Instruct), make both of them FINAL; our team will adjudicate them later.

ABOUT THE PROTOCOLS

The protocols below provide very detailed information for coding the university responses. Again, this coding is the process of creating standardized categories based on newspaper text.

There are four main questions (i.e. fields), each with many specific codes (i.e. thematic categories). For all four questions, you can select more than one code.

If you have any questions about an event, record your question in the appropriate column in the Assignments tab and raise it for discussion at a team meeting. If you realize that your coding of an article contains an **error** or **you accidentally didn't code an event**, please go back and fix your coding.

The Text-Based Content You Are Coding

When coding, for each Event ID, you should ***read all of the University Responses or Police Actions text carefully*** (possibly more than one "chunk" of text, each on a new row). Use that text to identify the appropriate categories in the protocol.

You also should ***read the (Original) Event Description***, which describes the overall protest. It may contain additional relevant information, and/or it may clarify anything that might be unclear in the text. If something is mentioned in the Event Description that is codeable but is not University Responses text, you should still code it. For example, sometimes not enough text is selected under University Responses (which was an error in the original coding) but more detail is in the Event Description. If the Event Description is vague but the text select is more specific, use the text select. For coding Police Actions: in particular, the Event Description may be relevant for identifying the protest location (which can influence the Type of Police) or the specifics of the Police Activities.

Using Information from Other Events

Sometimes you will know more about the university responses to a protest event than what is listed for that Original Event ID in the Data to Code tab. For example, you will likely come across codings of articles that contain multiple protests occurring at the same time, such as a protest and a counterprotest (which is a simultaneous protest that opposes the original protest and/or presents a contrary view on the issue). Sometimes, the text selected for one of those protests is more complete than the text selected for another protest within the same article (e.g. more complete for the protest than the counterprotest). In these cases, you should use information from the more complete text select to fill in any missing information for the less complete protest, *as long as you are certain it is accurate*. However, if you come across a protest event that was reported on and coded in two different articles (i.e., two newspapers covered the same event), do not use information from one article to inform your coding for the other article.

A few protests are very high profile and reported on in many articles, most notably the University of Missouri-Columbia (“Mizzou”) anti-racism protests in fall 2015. In the University Responses to Significant Protests section below, there is additional guidance for coding those.

Additional Contextual Information about the Original Protest Coding

Issues and Racial Issues

An “issue” has a very specific meaning in this project. “Issues” are what the protest is about and/or the reason(s) why people are protesting. It’s the core matter at hand. An issue might include any important actions or events that inspired or triggered the protest (e.g., a police shooting, a university president’s email, another protest event that protesters are showing solidarity with). Further, the project differentiates between (non-racialized) “Issues” and “Racial Issues” because we gather more detailed information on Racial Issues. Many protests involve both Issues and Racial Issues, sometimes raised by protestors as intersectional issues. Note that we often use the term “issues” as a catchall to refer to both Issues and Racial Issues.

Examples of Issues include: Economy/Inequality, Environmental, Faith-based discrimination, Far Right/Alt Right (Against), Far Right/Alt Right (For), Trump (Against), Trump (For), Transgender Issues (For), Transgender Issues (Against), and many more. Examples of Racial Issues include: Anti-Racism, Campus Climate, Hate Speech, Police Violence (race-related), University Governance/Policies/Programs (race-related), White Supremacy (Against), White Supremacy (For), and many more.

Campus Places

Within the text select and/or Event Descriptions, sometimes names of places or buildings on campus are referenced without full explanation. Typically this happens because the journalist assumes that readers are students who are familiar with the campus or nearby city/town landmarks. Examples: “Low” (a building name), “the Union” (referring to a student union, which in the U.S. is a campus building or space within a building), “Diag” (a central crosswalk, e.g. at Univ of Michigan), “the mall” (a central lawn or courtyard- not a shopping mall). This primarily is relevant for coding Police Actions, when determining the Type of Police.

UNIVERSITY RESPONSES PROTOCOL: FIELDS & CODES

Definition: University Responses

The “University” includes named and unnamed administrators (e.g., spokespeople) and units such as offices and departments (but not athletic coaches). “University Responses” refers to how university representatives manage protests by students, faculty, and staff. Although most protests tend to be discrete events bound by time and space, University Responses often are not. The administration might:

- respond to the reported (original) protest event
- respond to more than one protest, which may or may not be reported in that article
- acting on an issue but not evidently in response to a protest (although the journalist might suggest as much)
- prepare for an anticipated protest
- respond to a prior protest with an intention of influencing or preventing future protest
- spark another protest with their response, which can happen when protestors consider the response to be unsatisfactory.

The Protest Codebook definition of university responses provides the original instructions that coders followed when coding protest events:

“Highlight all text on the university or universities’ responses to the protest(s) - meaning, their actions in anticipation of, in reaction to the protest and/or in support of the protest. The actors may be named or unnamed university officials or named or unnamed units, e.g. the administration or the Department of Sociology. Depending on the article, this may be a lot of text compared to other Text Select categories. The text you select may include:

- quotes and who said them,
- the universities' position on the event. This often is what a university official says or the article's paraphrasing (e.g., calling the protest a unreasonable disruption),
- what a different university or officials from another university said about a protest taking place at a different university, or reactions they had to a protest at a different university (e.g. #11939: UofT officials react to a protest at McGill),
- the universities' efforts to prevent a protest
- the universities' tactical reaction to a protest (e.g. an official speaks to protestors),
- what the university says it will do regarding protestors' demands and grievances,
- programmatic and policy changes that the university actually implements,
- text noting that the university has not responded (avoidance is a response),
- and other content you see as appropriate.

Remember that **selecting more is better than less**, so try to capture as much as you can."

If a professor who is not in administration is targeted, e.g. to cancel class, with no response from the administration, do not code their actions/discourse as a university response, but put this text in Column B of the Assignments sheet: PROF TARGET

Organization of Questions

The protocol on University Responses contains four main questions. The first and second pertain to the protest itself, and the third and fourth pertain to the substantive issues the protestors are raising. Then, within each of these two question sets, there is one question that asks about University (re)actions and one that asks about University discourse:

“Protest/Issue,” “Low Bar,” and “High Bar” Categories

Some of the University Responses codes are labeled “PROTEST/ISSUE” and/or “LOW BAR” or “HIGH BAR.” These will make more sense as you get more familiar with the protocol.

PROTEST/ISSUE - This indicates that the code might not fit neatly under that particular question. Specifically, the university response may be focused on the protest, on the issue, or both or it may be vague.

LOW BAR - This is a more relaxed standard for coding. The university’s action or the meaning of their discourse can be more implicit. If you are uncertain whether the category applies, rely more on your own interpretation. When in doubt, code.

HIGH BAR - This is a stricter standard for coding. The university’s action or the meaning of their discourse should be explicit and very evident. Do not rely on your own interpretation of what might be implied. When in doubt, don’t code.

When an Event Has All “NA/Unclear” Answers

If you code an event as “NA/Unclear for all four questions, do not enter it into MPEDS. In the Assignments tab in Column F, write “All NA, not entered into MPEDS” and add the date in Column C.

Questions and Codes

University Reactions to Protest Events

The field captures the actions that university administrations take in reaction to protest events. Specifically, the university administration is reacting to (or anticipating) the protest, which is one type of political activity. The reactions may occur in the moment; this is short-term and in-the-moment strategic protest management - sometimes called negotiated management of crises and crowds. Their reactions may also happen before or after a protest event. The reactions may follow an established protocol, although that protocol likely is not transparent or known to the journalist.

- **Present** - Includes attending a protest but not evidently participating in it. Can include addressing protestors, observing protest from sidelines, leaving a building or office in order to listen to protestors. Do not code if administrators did not intend to attend the protest, e.g. happen to be passing by.
- **Instruct/Warn** - Ask or tell protestors that they need to or should do something; the protestors may or may not cooperate. E.g. Inform protestors that they must end the protest, disperse, or move the location of their protest; give instructions such as telling protestors

they cannot block access to a building or must write an apology (#1395); informing protestors they are trespassing or otherwise in violation of policy (eg. article #89) or that more police have been called in. May include conditions, e.g. an offer to have a meeting if protestors end a blockade. Verbal warnings have stated or implied consequences, e.g., threaten disciplinary action, tell protesters that the administration plans to call in the police to make arrests (eg. article #83). Includes statements or reminders that student protestors will face academic sanctions or grade penalties for missing class (#10570).

Exception: Includes actions that attempt to deter or undermine protestors by creating detrimental consequences but not “penalizing” the protestors, e.g., locking all washrooms, turning off utilities (#15321, event 15321) [\(In\)correct examples](#).

- **Direct (Broadly Distributed) Communications** - Email, letter, or “notification” distributed broadly, to all students (e.g. all undergraduates) or broader campus community. It should be circulated beyond just the protestors and/or the journalist. Text should be explicit that the communication was sent out broadly, not just “a statement from,” “said in an email” or “a press release.” If text specifically references that a letter was sent by an administrator without specifying to whom it was sent, still select this because it implies a level of formality and broad distribution in the context of relying on email (#16070). The rationale behind this definition is that the university took additional steps to enable a targeted and broad distribution, whereas a press release may only be sent to press outlets or posted on a webpage. Note that, below, you may also need to code the content of the communication, which could be about the protest and/or the issue; this code only applies to the act of communication. If the text select gives you reason to think the email was broadly distributed but it’s not entirely clear, check the original article text [\(In\)correct examples](#)
- **Meet with Protestors** - Administrators meet with, agree to meet with, or offer to meet with protestors (not just “students”) and/or protestors state that a meeting will or did happen. There is typically an indication that the administration agrees to the meeting because of the protest. A “meeting” also could take the form of a townhall clearly involving protestors (although this is less common) or an individual’s attendance at a particular meeting. A meeting between administration and protestors tends to have a specific goal/outcome. Other procedural actions, e.g., sharing a petition with the Board, typically would be coded as Action in Process. [\(In\)correct examples](#).
- **Refuse to Meet** - Refuse or decline a request to meet with protestors. The refusal should be explicit, not that the administration was unavailable for comment. A “meeting” also could take the form of a townhall or an individual’s attendance at a particular meeting. [\(In\)correct examples](#).
- **Get Confronted** - Protestors initiate and engage in (or try to engage in) confrontational face-to-face/physically proximate interaction with an administrator in ways that can disrupt standard procedure or norms of personal space or privacy. Examples include a sit-in in front of an administrator’s office or home (even if the occupant is not present), getting close to their body, surrounding them physically. Interpersonal interactions without physical

proximity should be coded if they invade personal privacy, e.g. posting an administrator's personal phone number and many people call it (but don't code if protestors spam a work phone number or email address, e.g. Event 6807). The purpose is to put pressure on the administrator to act on their political goal(s). Typically, in a confrontation, the protestors use their numbers and physical presence as a form of pressure, and they ask for a response (often a meeting) from an administrator in the moment. Their act of confrontation increases the intensity of the interaction between protestors and the administration. The administration typically is forced to acknowledge protestors. Often, administrators will respond by trying to constrain/limit/avoid the confrontation and minimize any disruption, such as shutting blinds to windows or leaving an event quickly.

This is more of a protest dynamic than a response, but it does involve administrators. Protestors' confrontation (or attempts at confrontation) are typically a part of protests that target the university and/or a university official to get their target's attention or agreement. The text should be explicit that protestors interact with, or attempt to interact with, a specific administrator, office, organized group (e.g. Trustees, Board), or a set of administrators- but not just an empty office. **Importantly, do not select if protestors only confront other targets, like guest speakers, or if administrators only respond to protestors confronting other targets.** [\(In\)correct examples.](#)

Protestors may do the following:

- Go to or try to go near someone's office for the confrontation.
- Attend or try to attend an in-person meeting or other event to which they were clearly not invited or not welcome, with the goal of face-to-face interaction (e.g., speak with or give the target literature, #17782)
- Attend a meeting or other event with the clear goal of disruption, via face-to-face interaction (#16070).
- Use their physical presence in an administrators' office to "create" a meeting (#1456/23726).
- Participate in an incursion into an administrators' personal/private space (e.g., protesting at someone's home, mass phone calling, email blast)

Potentially vague situations:

- It is not a confrontation if, during a protest, the administrator simply accepts a petition that has been delivered to them without confrontation, exits a building, makes an unpopular announcement, or gets booed by protestors. The confrontation is typically more dramatic than that.
- Often, protests inside an administration building will involve confrontation. However, only code for protests with a specifically targeted administrator or office,

not the general building (e.g., protestors gather for a sit-in, with no mention of a specific person or office they are trying to confront (#16340)).

- Delivering petitions only involves confrontation when protestors initiate a more confrontational physical interaction with a specific target.
- **Participate/Aid** - Administrators take part in the protest or aid the protestors, above and beyond university policies and practices that allow protest and generally ensure safety. Administrators participate by joining protest, e.g., march, hold a candle at a vigil. They aid by helping protestors deal with or prevent a (usually specific) problem or otherwise take actions that demonstrate support for the protestors, going to a police station to assist in the release of a student (eg. #2646), bringing water to protestors, keeping a building open to support a protest (#2305 - different than avoid penalize). Just providing a police presence/security for general safety purposes is not enough to qualify for this code. [\(In\)correct examples.](#) Uncommon.
- **Avoid Penalizing** - Intentionally not take action in ways that protect protestors from negative consequences, e.g., keeping a building open longer, intentionally not calling in the police (#2305), finding students guilty of violating the code of conduct but opting to issue warnings instead of fines, which were the initial threats (#16347). Likely, the administration is not following its own procedure or otherwise is changing rules to accommodate the protestors. For an occupation, the university's action to Avoid Penalizing needs to be more explicit than doing nothing (an occupation, by definition, typically involves the university not penalizing protestors, e.g. #2233). Uncommon.
- **No Intervention/No Assistance** - Administration intentionally does not intervene or does not change its policies and procedures in ways that would protect protestors, and this leads to or would likely lead to negative consequences for protestors, e.g. Quebec universities operate "business as usual" during the strike, so students face academic sanctions for missing class (#15075); not intervening in students getting arrested. This is a kind of contrary action, but do not also code Contrary Action (unless the university does something beyond not intervening). Code if a protestor alleges that the university could have intervened but didn't; take the protestor at their word.
- **End Protest** - University officials do something that causes the protest to end (other than fulfilling any of the protestors objectives) or that prompts the protestors to decide to end the protest (against the interests/objectives of the protestors), e.g., cut off access to washrooms (Event 17562), threaten to bring in the police. Likely will also code Instruct/Warn. Very uncommon. Do not code if:
 - university officials' instruct the police to end the protest,
 - the actions of the police or campus security ended the protest (Event ID 3731),
 - the protestors decide to end the protest because they achieved at least one of their goals and there was no pressure to end it by the administrators.

- **Penalize** - Proactively apply/implement or pursue institutional or legal penalties to punish protestors and/or their organization. Institutional penalties may include: discipline protestors and/or their organization, e.g., suspend/expel individuals, put on probation, revoke student group funding or charter. Legal penalties may include taking legal action against protestors and/or their organization, e.g., press charges or state that charges will be pressed, file a lawsuit against protestors or state that a lawsuit will be filed. Don't code for students facing academic sanctions for missing class because the university is not proactively trying to punish the student but rather making the student face the consequences of their academic decisions.
- **Revisit Protest P&P** - Administration reviews (or plans to review) and may change its policies on protest in anticipation of or in response to a protest (#974, 10880). This may not clearly be a reaction to the current protest; still code if relevant. Their reason for doing so may or may not be explicit; it could involve the protest actions, the issue(s) raised by protestors, or both. It's ok to infer that an institutional body that discusses the policy is "revisiting" (974)
- **NA/Unclear** - Not applicable because no text on protest management or unclear
- **Response to Protest Elsewhere** Select if the administration is responding to a protest at another university or college or a protest targeting a different university administration. E.g., an administrator at the Univ of Nevada condemns the Unite the Right march at Univ of Virginia #17028. Also fill in the information in the Response to Protest Elsewhere tab of the TO CODE sheet (the far right end of the tabs). Do not select this if the protest is targeting the government, e.g., concerning tuition increases, and the university administration responds. Very uncommon.

University Discourse: On Protest

This question refers to what administrators say (communicate) about protesting. "Discourse" refers to the language used by political, social, and institutional actors in social contexts, to characterize and give meaning to an issue, dispute, or group. Through discourse, university representatives make various claims about protest. They may be referring to this coded protest specifically, another protest, or protest in general. Their communication usually is verbal or else written; it could be quoted by the journalist or paraphrased; it could be stated to different people, e.g., the journalist, the protestors, an individual, etc. The communication could be before, during, or after the protest. Their communications before a protest (e.g. "Not following P&P/Law") might end up changing some aspect of the protest; still code these. When analyzing their discourse, focus on the quotes from university representatives and any paraphrasing of their words by the journalist (e.g., "an administrator stated that the students violated the policy"). With paraphrasing - when in doubt, look for reasonable indications that the information was a stated or written message from the university. If someone other than the administrator or journalist is making a claim about what the administration said, bring that up for discussion.

- **On Protest: Positive** - State or suggest that protesting is a positive, valuable way to engage politically. E.g., using language about “supporting” the protest, affirming the value of protest, describing the protest as peaceful, uniting people, representing many different groups, encouraging important conversations, expressing shared values, etc.

Do not select:

- If the protests are part of an event that the university is collaborating on, such as a dialogue/forum dedicated to discussing the issues raised (and esp if the text is vague), then do not select this because it is not noteworthy if the university says something positive about its own event, e.g. Earth Day protest and events #1484.
 - If the comments seem more like vague platitudes, e.g. “I express our appreciation for the views of those who were opposed to” this event (#1554) or the president “supports the right of students, faculty and staff to engage in thoughtful and respectful dialogue” (#4371).
- **On Protest: Exercising Free Speech** - Characterize this protest or protest generally as expressions of free speech/freedom of expression/self-expression/free speech, constitutional/First Amendment rights, the right to protest (peaceful assembly under the First Amendment). Often includes a reference to **“express” views or opinions and/or “rights” to voice views**. May or may not be critical of the protest. For example, administrators describe protestors as “exercising free speech, “expressing themselves” (eg. #2300), getting their voices heard (#2701). They may praise protestors for expressing their opinions peacefully (#19784); in that case, also code as Protest- Positive. This is distinct from text regarding “Listen/Dialogue,” defined below.
 - **On Protest: Obstructing Free Speech** - Criticize protestors for (allegedly) censoring or interfering with others’ free speech. “Paxson’s emails argued for the importance of free expression and protest, as long as they occur under ‘acceptable means.’ But, Paxson wrote, the means by which protestors stopped Kelly’s lecture were unacceptable and a violation of the code of conduct.” (#6628).
 - **On Protest: Violating P&P/Law** - Administrators state that protestors are breaking university rules, policies, procedures (eg. 11033 - the rally on the school premises disobeyed noise rules) or the law. And/or state that protestors need to abide by the university’s procedures and policies for protesting and/or the law, e.g., describe a protest as “unlawful assembly,” tell protestors they should have applied for permit. Tell protestors to register as a student org. There needs to be evidence that there was a public message from the university about the violation (quoted or paraphrased, e.g. #11411)). **For formal accusations and charges that involve violating law or policy, do not code if there is no clear public announcement by the university**, e.g. the text only contains the journalist’s description of, say, legal charges or a violation of a code of conduct, e.g., the protestors are the ones who told the journalist of being accused of a violation (#18053, Event 30384), or the text says

something such as: two students from the event ... have been accused of breaching the Student Code of Conduct (#956/9614).

- **On Protest: Disruptive** - Characterize protest as disruptive and/or interrupting normal affairs, with negative impacts for students, staff, patients, others on campus, or the university at large. The administration may describe the protest as disruptive and/or they may focus more on “detrimental” (#1187) consequences. Administrators commonly point to negative consequences for learning, e.g. describing Islamophobic flyers as a problem because they “compromise the learning environment” (#16801). Select this if the administration more generally references the problem of disruptive protests, e.g. “The college will also be conducting an additional review to prevent what it calls ‘attempts to disrupt college programs in a non-peaceful, materially disruptive way’” (16953).

Do not code if the administration makes no explicit mention of a disruption caused by a protest and there are no clear references to disruption, e.g., a spokesperson vaguely describes a protest as “crossing a line” (#4415).

- **On Protest: Illegitimate or Inappropriate** - Critique the protest form/action as not legitimate and/or not what the protestors claim it to be, e.g. saying a Quebec student strike is a “boycott” not a “strike,” when graduate students organize a union but administration will not recognize it. Includes statements that (the) protest (or some part of it) is an ineffective or inappropriate method of political engagement (e.g., suggesting that protest puts unreasonable pressure on an administrator to meet or act immediately #1456). Do not select this for administrators’ statements opposing unionization if they do not comment on the specific actions like strikes (#19693).
- **On Protest: Other Problem/Negative** - Refer to problems not listed in the categories above or generally characterizes the protest as negative. E.g., administrator states that a day of strikes cost the university \$10 million (#1035), protesters wrote a letter to an invited speaker, this led that speaker to decline the invitation, and then an administrator said this was “regrettable” (#1554). Don’t select this automatically just because one or more of the other negative codes above applied. Select when there are negative sentiments not captured in any of the above categories; you may select this with other negative codes or not, depending on the text. LOW BAR.
- **Listen/Dialogue** - State or suggest that the protest is a dialogue and/or that making progress going forward will or should involve listening, hearing, dialogue, conversation, discussion, and talking (#4459, #1456) e.g. the president stated “we encourage the campus community to use this opportunity to foster constructive dialogue toward solving some of our nation's most critical challenges” (#13983). PROTEST/ISSUE, e.g., calls for listening and dialogue might be a response to protest (e.g., listening is better than yelling) and/or about addressing the issue (e.g., dialogue can solve this problem), or it may not be clear if the calls for listening are responding to protest or to the issue. Includes calls for conversation/getting voices heard during labor or union contract negotiations - but more than saying there is a need for negotiation (Event 17226).

- **Work w/ Protesters** - Explicit statements by administrators that they are working with (or plan to work with) protestors to address the issues, e.g. by engaging in problem solving collaboratively. E.g., the president “said she would work with [Black Students United] to “do everything we can to rid this campus of racism” (#17540). The administration is suggesting protestors are legitimate political actors to engage with and/or that it is acting in good faith. Protestors may or may not agree that the administration is working with them. Protestors and/or the movement organization need to be clearly referenced - not just the populations (e.g., racialized students) whom protestors claim to represent. This should be more than a suggestion that the administration and students should or could work together (so, not “I encourage people to work with me” #1456), having a meeting, or saying that protest is positive. Do not code for statements by administrators only saying that they are negotiating or will negotiate with activists (which is esp. common with union organizing); do not code if the university’s discourse suggests they are only fulfilling a formal/bureaucratic obligation to negotiate with the union organizers (or other activists).
- **Safety** - State a concern with security and/or protecting the safety of students, staff, and faculty or property in the context of possible threats. E.g., stated to justify bringing in a large police presence or ending a protest. Includes statements that protest makes students feel unsafe and/or that protest was violent. PROTEST/ISSUE: Administration often raises safety as a concern around far-right events, e.g. Milo Yiannopoulos speaking. (#19784). However, the exact cause of safety concerns (a protest such as a hunger strike? the triggering event?) may be vague. Do not code administrators’ vague statements about “safety and well being” of students that are not explicitly or clearly connected to the protest (#4433).
- **Protest “Policing Problems”** - Administration and/or police refer to problems with how the protest was policed, such as criticism, an apology, a statement of disapproval. e.g., “we cannot condone any excessive use of [police] force against any members of our community” (eg. article #103). Do not select if administrators describe policing more general or a specific police interaction with a non-protestor as problematic. Do not select if policing is only a protest issue, e.g. police brutality. Uncommon.
- **NA/Unclear** - No text on the University’s discursive claims on protest or unclear.

University Action on Issues

What the university administration does in regards to the protestors’ substantive position, asks, demands for change, etc. This could be action already taken, ongoing action, or statements that action will be taken in the future. It includes inaction. Note that this action is often communicated through discourse - i.e., in statements and quotes from administrators; we are treating that discourse as factually true. The reasons for the (in)action could be the protest and/or other factors or vague.

- **Hold Forum** - with students/community to discuss issue(s) raised by the protest, e.g., administrators hold forums, listening sessions, and other events to share perspectives, educate, learn from students. Not mental health services, involving security, or press conferences. A forum is more open than a meeting and tends to have a broader range of participants and a different purpose, e.g. hearing different views.
- **Action in Process** - References to bureaucratic process and procedure (e.g. a plan, committee, task force, or meeting) or statements or offers of planned bureaucratic change in future (or unclear timing) toward working on the issue(s) raised by protestors. This is typically **an implied or explicit recognition that the bureaucratic status quo is insufficient and an implied or explicit commitment to working on something to change that status quo. However, it is not the actual solution.** Exactly what steps the university will take to address the issue, if any, is generally vague. Examples: incorporate student demands into a diversity and inclusion plan (#1302), state that administrators will share protestors' proposal with the Board of Trustees, explore the Calls for Action that came out the Truth & Reconciliation Commission (#20320), work with a student group to "do everything we can to rid this campus of racism" (#17540).

Includes situations when the university is not the (only) target and the administration is engaging in political or bureaucratic advocacy and it likely shares a common target with the protestors. E.g., the administration tells the provincial/state government that more funds are needed (#10662, #18214). In this advocacy, the university may use a form that protestors are pushing for, such as signing a petition or a sending collective letter from universities (#14224). Do not code administrators' acknowledgement of issues or demands that do not also reference institutional activity, e.g. statements that what protestors want is "reasonable or actionable" (#1302). LOW BAR.

- **Preset** - A new or revived service offered over a semester or a shorter time period - counseling, support groups, healing circle, holding a prayer (Event #23610), e.g., "Dean Stiglitz notified the community of ... a Healing Circle for all black women, which will meet weekly throughout the semester" (#1302).
- **Structural Change** - A change in institutional policy, program, positions (e.g., a new position), roles/job description, or organization that works toward the protestor's general goal for the issue or a decision has been made to act. The timing of when the activity starts may be vague; it can be already underway but it should be a change from prior (in)action - not an administrator saying "we already do X." E.g., a stated commitment to hire 5 new faculty, a new course requirement on racism, an agreement to expand a multiculturalism centre, writing a university land acknowledgement, creation of new opportunity programs or scholarships for certain groups of students (#12278) or a new position such as Chief Diversity Officer. Includes stated commitments to protect undocumented students' data and provide them with resources, such as legal counsel and keeping their information private from law enforcement (#16987); this may not clearly be a change in university policy, but it is a reaction to a change in U.S. immigration policy.

For labor issues, bring this up for discussion; examples of structural change for labor would be an increase in wages or improved conditions of work or benefits in a contract and the protestors agree with this (e.g., if the text describes the conditions of the contract and also gives an indication that they are an improvement; assertions by a union that the new contract is better). Do not code for unionization, simply a new contract (with no indication it contains improvements), or a tentative agreement (e.g., Event 17505 - that would be Action in Process, do not code vague statements (e.g., Event 10578).

- **Resign/Fire** - An administrator, professor, staff, trustee/board member (or other university non-student person in a position of power) resigns, is fired, or is removed from their position, e.g. a president resigns after being targeted by protestors and criticized as racist. This action should be plausibly relevant to a protest, although it may be unclear if the action is entirely due to the protest. HIGH BAR.
- **Sanction** - An administrator, professor, staff, trustee/board member (or other university non-student person in a position of power) is suspended from pay, put on leave, banned from campus temporarily, courses canceled, etc (#23367). This action should be plausibly relevant to a protest, although it may be unclear if the action is entirely due to the protest. HIGH BAR.
- **Correct Racist History** - Ongoing activity, plan, or stated commitment to, e.g., change the name of a building or a sports team mascot, remove a statute, remove a Confederate flag, a committee to examine the role of slavery in the university's founding (4688), any action involving "reparations" (very uncommon). Often, it is implied or outright stated that the university is recognizing (usually past) wrongdoing and the need to repair this wrongdoing, the university's legacy, and/or its public image. **Do not select Structural Change if this is the only structural change in the text** (although this does fit that definition). Uncommon. HIGH BAR.
- **Cancel Speaker/Event** - A scheduled or invited speaker or event is canceled before, during, or after a protest in opposition to that speaker. It does not matter who decided to cancel, e.g. the university, another group (e.g. College Republicans), the speaker, etc. PROTEST/ISSUE: Select this if the speaker is canceled prior to the planned protest even if the university gives a vague reason for the cancellation such as "safety concerns" (which usually mean potential violence between protestors, counterprotestors, and/or bystanders), e.g., #12349 or if an invited speaker declines after a protest against them (#1554). The cancellation could be a response to a prior protest and/or it could be the triggering event for a protest, e.g. UC-Berkeley canceled Ann Coulter's talk after contentious protests around an earlier talk by Milo Y (#16785). HIGH BAR.
- **Compromised Action on Demand Issue** - University action or activities that engage and/or partially address the issue; entails a change in course from the status quo that moves closer toward the protestors goals (rather than contrary to their goals) but does not fulfill the protestor's demand(s). Typically, these actions do not involve extensive resource

commitments, significant costs, or other serious concessions on the part of the university. Examples: change in the time of Tyga’s concert when protestors demanded a cancellation (#469), reassigning current Title IX investigators who focused on faculty to focus on students in response to a demand for hiring a new investigator (#XXX). Could be both Compromised Action and Reject Demand (e.g., 3884). For a labour protest, code if the university makes an offer that improves conditions somewhat but is rejected by protesters, e.g., a very modest wage increase.

- **Fulfill Demand** - Administration fulfills or makes a decision to fulfill (partially or completely) at least one of protestors’ specific demands/asks/requests regarding the protest issue, or it states that demand has been fulfilled or is currently being fulfilled (not just Action in Process). Protestors need to be clearly asking for a specific action or change. This typically is when the university is the target. The administration may or may not explicitly mention that this organizational change was in response to an activist demand. Believe administrators if they state that they are taking actions that protestors are requesting (#1302). The university may fulfill a demand by signing a petition or taking a similar procedural action. HIGHEST BAR.

The administration may fulfill the demand partially; consider if the protestors would view this this as a victory, E.g., student protestors called for a full-time coordinator for students without documentation and “the university has hired Arelis Palacios as its new part-time coordinator for students without documentation” (#14224). If the protestors have a specific ask, e.g. hire a new Title IX investigator (Event 23952), and the university’s response works toward the same goal but uses different means, e.g., shuffling job descriptions, do not code as Fulfill Demand.

For the sanctuary campus movement: Select this option if the university implements (or announces existing) [policies to protect](#) students and/or faculty who are undocumented immigrants. Those policies can vary, e.g., barring immigration officers without a warrant from campus, refusing to share information about faculty or students’ immigration status with ICE absent a court order; or implementing a “don’t ask, don’t tell” policy on student immigration status. The policies may be vague, e.g. “Hamilton said that the university is enforcing a number of policies to protect the privacy and personal information of undocumented students and immigrants on campus” #16070.

Do not code if:

- The administration generally is positive toward the demands, e.g. the president describes protestors’ list of demands as ‘reasonable and actionable.’” (#1302).
- The administration is taking vague “Action in Process” on the demands, e.g., “University of Missouri President Tim Wolfe says ... the majority of items that Concerned Student 1950 listed in their demands were in the [diversity] strategy that’s being worked on” (#4417).

- It is ambiguous or unlikely that the administration's actions satisfy a demand. Often, administrators will characterize actions they are taking on a general issue, but these actions are not, or are not clearly, related to the actions that protestors have requested (#3385).
- Only a protestor, not the administration, claims that the administration is expressing support.
- Do not code a meeting between protestors and administration as fulfilling a demand, even if there was a demand for a meeting.
- In a labour protest, the university and activists come to a contractual agreement but the text does not specify if demands in the strike/protest were met.

Likely at least one other option for this same question, e.g. Structural Change, Cancel Speaker, Resign/Fire should also be selected.

- **Reject Demand** - Refuse to fulfill at least one of these protestors' demands/asks/ requests **related to the issues raised by the protest**; this could be stated by an administrator or by the journalist. The rejection should be an explicit communication or explanation that the university will not take action toward the protestors' goal (e.g., "We will not," "The dean stated that the university cannot do..." or an explicit defense of the status quo that signals the demand is being rejected such as "We will continue our practice of XYZ because...") and directly in response to the current protest. Protestors need to be clearly asking for a specific action or change. The demand rejected typically is substantive and issue-based, e.g., divest from fossil fuels; For example, an administrator wrote in an email that the "sanctuary" designation 'lacks substantive meaning for policy and practice, but also sends a message that is interpreted inconsistently across the country'" (#15698). And/or the demand rejected could be procedural, such as refusing to sign onto a petition or list of demands for Latin@ Studies (#1456). HIGH BAR.

Do not code if:

- The administration only refuses to meet to discuss demands (e.g., #243) (because a meeting is about the process, not the specific issue)
- The journalist just states that the university has been in opposition to this position in the past, e.g. "University President Drew G. Faust has held a firm stance against divesting from fossil fuel investments, arguing that Harvard's endowment is not a tool for political and social activism. She instead advocates fighting climate change through research" (#6343). This is not a specific, direct rejection of what protestors are requesting.
- Protestors are opposing a speaker or other event and there is not more information in the text about whether they asked the university to cancel the event beforehand

and/or the university explicitly refused to do so, e.g. a protest during a White supremacist speaker #18053).

Likely, Express Contrary Position will also be selected.

- **No Cancellation of Speaker/Event** - The triggering event for the protest is a controversial speaker or event on campus (e.g., a talk by a White supremacist, Janet Napolitano at UC-Berkeley #1421) or an object such as a “free speech wall” (#18079) opposed by protestors, and no one cancels the event, e.g., the speaker/campaign is able to rent campus space. There could be many reasons for the lack of cancellation. The reason is not important and irrelevant to the category. Do not code it seems that protestors only disagree with the speaker’s views or prior action, esp. if they are protesting against an administrator; ideally, this is for protests against the existence of the event, e.g. the speaker’s opportunity to speak on campus, although that is not always clear from the text.
- **Contrary Action** - Proactively take action that works against the protestors’ position or requests on a substantive issue, above and beyond maintaining the status quo (e.g., keeping a fossil fuel-funded research center) and/or maintaining a contested plan (e.g., a plan to develop a tract of land, a plan to raise tuition).

With labour actions only - the issue and the protest may be more blurred, e.g. strikers are withholding labor to improve labor conditions, so those might be PROTEST/ISSUE. Includes efforts to minimize disruptions due to a labour strike (Event 19529).

This may involve aggressive action, e.g., hiring temporary workers to replace striking workers (Event 28048), “Harvard and peer institutions filed an amicus brief (i.e., a legal argument) against graduate student unionization earlier this month” (#6223 - for these sorts of legal actions, also select Penalize);. Uncommon.

- **NA/Unclear** - No text on the university’s actions on issues or unclear.

University Discourse: On Issues

This question refers to what administrators say (communicate) about the substantive issues that protestors are protesting about, e.g. tuition increases, labor disputes. Through discourse, university representatives make various claims about issues raised by or related to the protest.

To repeat: “discourse” refers to the language used by political, social, and institutional actors in social contexts, to characterize and give meaning to an issue, dispute, or group. Their communication usually is verbal or else written;; it could be quoted by the journalist or paraphrased; it could be stated to different people, e.g., the journalist, the protestors, an individual, etc. The communication could be before, during, or after the protest. When analyzing their discourse, focus on the quotes from university representatives and any paraphrasing of their words by the journalist. With paraphrasing - when in doubt, look for reasonable indications that the information was a stated or written message from the university. If someone other than the

administrator or journalist is making a claim about what the administration said, bring that up for discussion.

- **Express Agreement on Issue** - Administrators communicate or signal their alignment or agreement with protestors on at least one of the protestors' [Issues](#), [Racial Issues](#) and/or their general cause. E.g., "Ballard... expressed support for Stand in Solidarity" (#4661), the Office of Sustainability made a statement encouraging students to recycle on Earth Day (#1484). The administration may or may not express agreement with a more specific concern of the protestors, such as opposition to a Confederate flag on campus (#1840). The administration also may be engaged in advocacy or refer to actions it is taking to support that cause. The agreement may be genuine or disingenuous; the protestors may or may not believe the university. Needs to be more than explaining Action in Process. LOW BAR.

Do not code if:

- Administrators act like they agree yet shift the topic, e.g. protestors oppose corporate influence on the university's environmental research and the administration states its concern with "energy." e.g., Peabody Energy at Wash-U.
- Administrators make a generic/general statement that few people would disagree with. E.g. responding to a student kneeling to protest racism, the president writes, "I share with many the belief that our nation does not always live up to its highest ideals, including the equal rights we hold dear" (#17598). "Watered Down Completely"
- **Emotional Appeal** - Administrators refer to or express their own empathetic or sympathetic feelings toward protestors and/or students or other group whom protestors (claim to) represent, typically regarding how students are affected by an issue such as campus climate. PROTEST/ISSUE May be related to the issue and/or, occasionally, the protest. E.g. "I love you," "We care deeply," "I care about this institution ... and the experience of students," "[the Vice Chancellor] said she wanted to ... provide care and comfort for students" (#1657). Includes unpleasant emotions, e.g. pain, sadness about students' experience.

Do not code if

- it is a generic appeal to caring (e.g., an administrator expressed "voiced sympathy" #1456- too vague)
- a statement that the institution is concerned, (e.g. "it is ... deeply regrettable that we have lost an opportunity" #2388 or a statement "dubbing the arrest 'disturbing'" #19730).
- This emotion is about an issue alone (e.g., "he cares about energy") or a non-campus community/group affected by it.

- **Apology/Responsibility** - Administrators apologize or explicitly claim that a specific university official (e.g., a dean) and/or the university as an institution accepts responsibility for the issue, action, and/or related organizational situation. Needs to be more than acknowledging negative consequences of university action or inaction (#4843).
- **Explain the (Unchanged) Bureaucracy/Law** - Explaining standard procedures, processes, organizational structure, etc. regarding an issue (or ways to address the issue) with no suggestion that the bureaucracy has changed recently, will change, or should change, e.g. #1239. May be defensive or could have a positive valence, e.g., suggest the university already takes care of this problem. PROTEST/ISSUE LOW BAR

Includes:

- statements that an administrator (e.g., a dean) does not have authority to make the requested change.
- statements during labour negotiations that defend the university's employment practices and wages, e.g., "Meron said the UC's offer to AFSCME workers is fair, referencing that wages ... are currently above market rates" (#1187).
- statements about what the university can or cannot do legally
- legal explanations for (in)action, e.g., rejecting the "sanctuary campus" label.
- statements on how the law works in relation to the protestors' issue, e.g., ""although simply believing in white supremacy or belonging to a white supremacist group is not a crime, the federal government has successfully charged white supremacists over the years using federal statutes"" (Event 31631).

Do not code if the administration is only trying to use bureaucratic rules to say a protest is illegitimate, e.g. the administration claims "students are not bound by an employee collective agreement and, therefore, are not eligible to 'strike'" (#10570).

- **Express Contrary Position or Criticize** - Explicitly express a viewpoint that disagrees with the protestors' position/concerns - E.g., "University President Drew G. Faust has held a firm stance against divesting from fossil fuel investment" (#6343). And/or criticize or contradict protestors' claims by stating or suggesting that the protestors are wrong or misguided in their position/concerns on an issue, e.g. a statement that protestors are inaccurately calling free speech "harassment" (#18053) or are incorrect in their view that graduate students are employees (#19693), a claim that the university "did not intimidate employees" (#1027). Double check your coding to confirm if Take Contrary Action applies or not.
- **Affirm Free Speech when (Protestors' Make Accusations of) Bigotry** - Make positive comments about free speech in relation to a situation that protestors have characterized as racist or otherwise bigoted. Administrators may use terms such as free speech, freedom of expression, free expression, intellectual freedom, expression of ideas "even if offensive."

They may be responding to incidents, events, individuals, and groups that protestors have accused of being racist, homophobic, transphobic, Islamophobic, anti-Semitic, or otherwise bigoted (e.g., #17028/31795). E.g., responding to protest against a White supremacist speaker, an administrator wrote: “harassment must necessarily mean something more than being subjected to expression of ideas that any of us considers loathsome or even dangerous” (#18053) (in other words, they said that racist speech does not rise to the level of racist harassment). Includes calls to counter offensive speech with “more speech,” e.g. “I think the students that are organizing today’s march are doing exactly what we hoped they would, which is counter speech with other forms of speech,” (#18079). Don’t code if the issue is only abortion (e.g., affirming graphic posters as free speech) without an accusation of bigotry such as religious discrimination or sexism. PROTEST/ISSUE. HIGH BAR.

- **Affirm Diversity** - Make positive references to these or very similar terms: “diversity,” “inclusion,” “equity,” “multiculturalism,” inclusive community. Could also be affirmation of “differences” in backgrounds, “perspectives,” “viewpoints,” and experiences, implying a mix is a good thing. The message may be subtle, e.g. the university president says “we must be vigilant in respecting others’ opinions and understanding our differences in backgrounds, perspectives and experiences.” (#13983). May sound wishy-washy and feel-good, can imply that the most fundamental differences between people are their viewpoints and backgrounds. May also be selected with Listen/Dialogue. HIGH BAR.
- **Affirm BIPOC Students** - Acknowledge and/or make positive references to the presence of BIPOC students on campus, to BIPOC students’ needs to feel safe, welcome, not harassed, legitimate members of the campus community. May include recognition of challenges BIPOC students face and their needs for resources, e.g. mental health support. Often but not always includes an emotional valence and concern with feelings. Should contain an explicit reference to Black or Indigenous students, students of colour, and/or another racialized category of students or acknowledgement of differential treatment/harms for Black students. HIGH BAR
- **Affirm Marginalized Students (other than BIPOC)** - Acknowledge and/or make positive references to the existence, needs, concerns of categorically marginalized students (other than BIPOC students) - those who would be those targeted and/or most harmed by an issue. Look for references to specific student demographic groups or acknowledgement of differential treatment/harms. Groups include women (eg, in context of sexual assault), LGB+, trans students, Muslim, Jewish, students with disabilities, undocumented, low-income students, etc. This category is esp. common with immigration issues and LGB+ and trans issues. Includes these students’ needs to feel safe, welcome, not harassed, legitimate members of the campus community as well as recognizing challenges these students face and needs for resources, e.g. mental health support. Includes sanctuary movement responses such as, “[Executive VP] Monaco pledged to support and protect undocumented students” (#16987). Often but not always includes an emotional valence and concern with feelings. HIGH BAR

- **Oppose Racism** - The university explicitly opposes, condemns, criticizes racism/systemic racial oppression. Can include racial discrimination, racial bias, racial hate speech, racial oppression. Includes Islamophobia and anti-Semitism if explicitly racialized. Can include recognition of disparities between racial groups, e.g. Black students carry more student loan debt. Should be more specific than “intolerance” or vaguely “hate.” HIGH BAR
- **Oppose Oppression/Bigotry (other than racism)** - The university explicitly opposes, condemns, criticizes at least one form of systemic oppression/inequality/ -ism. E.g., sexism, homophobia, anti-trans, Islamophobia, anti-Semitism, classism. Can include (non-racialized) hate speech, hatred against a specific group, bigotry. Can include recognition of inequalities and disparities between groups, e.g. the university is condemning unequal pay for women and men employees. Should be more specific than “intolerance” or vaguely “hate.” HIGH BAR
- **NA/Unclear** - Not applicable because no text on discourse on issue or unclear

University Responses to Significant Protests

Below are fields that are *likely* to be relevant to certain types of protests, although you should always make selections based directly on the text.

Mizzou 2015 Anti-Racism Protests

Likely relevant fields for references to university leaders stepping down, e.g., the university president.

- Univ Reaction to Protest: If article only says Wolfe refused to speak, don't code as Refuse to Meet
- Univ Action on Issue: Resign/Fire, Fulfill Demand

Note: Wolf's resignation technically wasn't a demand until after the homecoming parade parade, because Wolf's actions at that parade motivated protestors to demand that he step down, but for simplicity we will code it as such.

Quebec 2012 Student Strikes

University does not give academic amnesty for protestors who miss classes during strike:

Likely relevant fields:

- Univ Reaction to Protest: No Intervention, Instruct/Warn
- Univ Discourse on Protest: Protest: Disruptive, Protest: Illegitimate
- Univ Action on Issue: Reject Demand

- Univ Discourse on Issue: Express Contrary Position

Far Right Speakers, “Hate Speech” Events

Likely relevant fields:

- Univ Discourse on Protest: “Safety,” Protest: Exercising and/or Obstructing Speech
- Univ Action on Issue: Cancel Speaker/Event or No Cancellation
- Univ Discourse on Issue: Affirm Free Speech when Bigotry

2016 Sanctuary Campus Movement

Likely relevant fields:

- Univ Action on Issue:
 - Structural Change (if adopting protective policies)
 - Fulfill Demand (if already have or are adopting protective policies)
 - Reject Demand (e.g., if won’t adopt “sanctuary campus” label)
- Univ Discourse on Issue:
 - Affirm Marginalized Students
 - Explain the Bureaucracy/Law (e.g., if explain legal reasons univ isn’t adopting the label)

Labour Negotiations

Likely relevant fields:

- Univ Action on Protest: Not Applicable
- Univ Discourse on Protest
 - On Protest: Disruptive
 - On Protest: Illegitimate only if the administrators say that unionization is not necessary (b/c they’re talking about the Issue, not the protest)
- Univ Action on Issue:
 - Action in Process (e.g., negotiations in process or pending),

- Contrary Action (e.g., trying to disrupt a strike)
- Univ Discourse on Issue: Express Contrary Position, Explain Bureaucracy/Law (e.g., explain negotiation process works)

Notes on Labour protests from June 2022 meeting notes:

- University responses to labor protests are often not coded because they tend to follow pro forma actions and discourse, e.g. calling for negotiations, praising the acceptance of an settlement offer. Also, we did not capture canceling classes in the coding because it wasn't clearly aiding or working against the protestors.
- Cancelling classes could be undermining the protest (lessening the chaos) and/or doing what protestors want (causing disruption).

Text Examples of University Responses

The purpose of this section is to provide examples of certain codes, to give coders a clearer picture and understanding of what text is codable and what text isn't. Distinctions regarding similar text will be made to help coders pinpoint where a text becomes codable. This section is supposed to serve as an additional resource to reassure and guide coders as they read through text. Note: this section was created with the assumption that the reader has already studied the Codebook Supplement and some knowledge of it. It is important that the reader primarily reviews the Codebook Supplement first as these resources do not contain an exhaustive description of the categories.

University Responses to Protest Events

Present

Correct Example	Incorrect Example
<p>"Vice Chancellor Kang addressed the crowd gathered at Meyerhoff Park in front of Kerckhoff Hall." (#4160).</p>	<p>"CSU Chancellor Charles Reed spoke with the . . . strikers on the topic of their demands on May 4." (#251)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Difference?</p> <p>Although at face value they can both appear to involve the physical presence of administrators in response to protestors. However, what makes the second example incorrect is that the timing of when the chancellor spoke with the strikers is vague; it could have been during or after the protest.</p> <p>Key Take Away: You must pay close attention to the environment in which the presence was made (i.e., must be during the protest event). Do NOT assume that the protestors/issue claimants only exist in a protest event setting.</p>	

Instruct/Warn

Correct Example	Incorrect Example
<p>"Dean of Undergraduate and Graduate Students John Barker told TCA members about possible non-permanent record sanctions for seniors during the sit-in. McMahon also previously told the Daily that TCA students were informed about disciplinary procedures" (#4013)</p>	<p>"Campus staff members also put up signs in front of the gate with instructions on how to circumvent the gate." (#3385)</p>

	Difference?
	<p>Although both examples appear to show the university managing the protest by releasing instructions, what is important to note is to whom those instructions are issued to and what are the implications of those instructions. In this case, the incorrect examples fall into the monitor/present instead instruct/warn because it is not clear that the instructions provided were for the protestors and/or other campus visitors.</p> <p>Key Take Away: Identifying the target of the instructions/warning (i.e., protestors) is what ultimately qualifies the text as instruct/warn.</p>

Direct Communications

Correct Example	Incorrect Example
<p>“While the black students have called for a concrete list of changes on campus, the all-campus emails from Nair, Student Government Association and College Council don't even reference the demands or attempt to discuss possible changes to address racial injustice on campus.” (#4717)</p>	<p>“In a public statement on March 7 ... he called for active threat preparedness.” (#19294)</p>
	Difference?
	<p>Although both appear to be delivering a message about the protest/issue to the campus community, the method in which it is delivered matters. Only certain mediums of communication are coded as per the codebook, these are “<i>Email, letter, or “notification” to all students</i>”). General public statements are NOT included because it is not clear who could have heard/received them.</p> <p>Key Take Away: Pay attention to the method of communication. Strictly select for emails, letters, or notifications. Anything outside should be disregarded even if it logically makes sense to you.</p>

Meet

Correct Example	Incorrect Example
“Paxson reached out to NAB members to discuss changing the name of Fall Weekend, and the group plans on scheduling a meeting soon” (#4201).	‘During the rally itself, more than 100 protesters marched around the Hall chanting until Marc Goodheart, the secretary of the Harvard Corporation and the University VP collected the petition. (#481)
<p style="text-align: center;">Difference?</p> <p>Although both parties interact with administrators, it is important to note that “meet” does not just mean a physical interaction (or intent for one) but rather also an interaction that includes some sort of dialogue (or a plan for some dialogue) between the two parties. The incorrect example lacks an interaction where greater dialogue takes place.</p> <p>Key Take Away: Identify both a physical interaction AND an interaction with the purpose of creating dialogue and communication.</p>	

Refuse to Meet

Correct Example	Incorrect Example
“When asked about a meeting with CEP during a Student Government General Assembly meeting on November 2, Isaacs said that he would not meet with CEP because he considered the General Assembly meeting the most appropriate place to discuss the UCPD. (#4376)	“Following rising racial tensions at Mizzou, a group of student protesters stood in front of Tim Wolfe's car in the middle of the homecoming parade procession. Wolfe never moved from his vehicle to speak with the protestors” (#4466)

	Difference?
	<p>Although both texts describe a refusal by administrators to interact with the protestors, the difference lies in how it was communicated. Specifically note how in the correct example, the administrator clearly states and communicates his intent to not interact with protestors. In contrast, the incorrect example does not, and it is left to the coder to assume that the individual is refusing to meet.</p> <p>Key Take Away: Only select for <i>explicit</i> text describing a refusal/intent to refuse. Never assume.</p>

Get Confronted

	Correct Example	Incorrect Example
	<p>“Approximately 50 protestors gathered with banners and signs on the lawn outside University President Anthony Monaco's door at 6 p.m. on Halloween - where Monaco annually greets trick-or-treaters - and asked for a dialogue with the administration.” (#4371)</p>	<p>“Professional Staff Congress (PSC) union at Queens College organized a mass disruption rally to pressure CUNY for a new contract.” (#4386).</p>
	Difference?	
	<p>Although both events seem to show protestors applying strong pressure to their respective universities to get attention, the difference lies in the available information in the text. In the correct example, it is clear who is in the specific administrative target (<i>specific administrator, office, body (e.g. Trustees, Board)</i>), the large number of protestors, and how they effectively forced themselves on the target. In contrast, the incorrect example only gives a relatively vague description on how the protestors are pressuring the university. There is no specific target mentioned and no specific description of how the event unfolded or sought to create confrontation.</p> <p>Key Take Away: Look for <i>explicit</i> text that directly describes an intent to create a confrontation with a specified target and protest pressure details.</p>	

Participate/Aid

Correct Example	Incorrect Example
<p>“About 100 students gathered to participate in a rally, organized by the League of Student Voters, and listen to speakers, which included administration and other members of the WSU community, who spoke out against cuts to higher education which would lead to a 16% tuition hike.” (#357)</p>	<p>“The Department of University Ministry set up signs near the display advertising counseling services for post-abortive women” (#19720)</p>
	<p style="text-align: center;">Difference?</p> <p>Although both appear to show the university being actively involved in the protest in a way which can be beneficial towards the protest goals, there is a strong difference present. The difference lies in how in the correct examples has explicit text describing how the administration became a part of the protest towards furthering its goals. In contrast, the incorrect example lacks clear text describing how their actions contribute towards furthering the protest.</p> <p>Key Take Away: Look for <i>explicit</i> intent and/or actions by the university to further the protest. If you have to assume then do not code.</p>

POLICE ACTIONS PROTOCOL: FIELDS & CODES

Definition: Policing

The codebook definition of police actions provides the original instructions that Coders followed when coding this protest event:

“The activities of the security forces mentioned in the article who are related to the event and the things they did at the event, e.g. present at the event, monitor the event, make arrests. Also select any quotes from security forces. Use this for government police and university police/campus security. With each text selection, try to capture enough content so we can tell who did what--either the campus police or the government police (e.g. “the campus police were present”); capture complete sentences whenever possible. When in doubt, overselect the potentially relevant text.”

Note that “Police actions,” refers to the actions taken by police when they are overseeing and responding to protests by students, faculty and staff. We are not analyzing how police act toward people who are not participating in this protest event, such as Officer Darren Wilson's murder of Michael Brown (that might be the protest “issue,” but it is not about how this protest event was policed). In other words, a protest may be about problems with policing, but the only police actions that you should code should be *protest policing*. If you see text selected in your spreadsheet that you suspect should not have been selected for this reason, make a note of it in your spreadsheet and notify Ellen or Kristen.

To repeat: for some protest events, text about policing was selected as a University Response. Typically, those are statements to the press by police leaders. You should code that information in the Policing section of the protocol, too, as if it were in the Police Actions column.

Code policing using the text in the spreadsheet. (This is unlikely, but you might notice that within the MPEDS interface, some policing text is not visibly selected. This is because, for early coding in the project, there was a separate category for “Police [names]” that, on the backend, has been merged with “Police actions.”)

Questions and Codes

For each of the following categories, select all options that apply. If the information is overly vague or not noted, select either “unclear” or “not relevant.” While making your selections, copy and paste the relevant text select chunks in the box provided for each question. If there is more than one chunk of text, separate by a semi-colon. **In these definitions, the term “police” encompasses police officers (employed by the university or by the government), “cops,” special constables**

(in Canada), campus safety, campus security, public safety, protective services (U of Saskatchewan), Secret Service, private security, and other kinds of security.

See below for instructions specific to each category.

Types of Police

"Police" may be used to refer to campus security, government police, or both; sometimes it is vague. Often, police are identified by an acronym, such as SPVM (Service de Police de la Ville de Montréal). If the acronym includes a U, it is most likely campus police. If you cannot determine an acronym (e.g. #2300, #2510), search for the acronym + the publication or university name on the internet or check the original article, whichever is quicker.

Select the types of police that are mentioned in the Police Action text. There may be more than one department involved, in which case, select all that apply (e.g. university police *and* city police). If a police department is named, assume all police actions are done by that department.

- **University police** - E.g. "campus security," "public safety officers," "campus safety." The police should be named (e.g. University of California-Berkeley police) or described as campus police (e.g. campus security). If the name is City + State, e.g. San Francisco State police, that refers to campus police.
- **University police - assumed** - the police department is not named but
 - the protest occurs entirely or primarily on campus or
 - the protest occurs partially on campus and involves a large disruption that would affect campus activity (eg. #2495 - a 500 person march and blockade disrupt traffic in an intersection bordering campus, stopping the campus circulator)
 - the protest occurs partially on campus and the protestors are physically near high level administrators (e.g., outside a building where the Board of Governors is meeting; occupying a building with the president's office)

Do not select if it is clear that government police were involved and the protest happens partially on campus but does not fit the 3 criteria above and there is no other indication of involvement of campus police.

- **Government police** - Municipal, state/provincial, federal, park police - any police department run by a government entity (other than a university). The police should be named (e.g. Chicago Police Department, Sûreté du Québec) or described as government police (e.g. state troopers). If the text is vague but the actions happen entirely off campus and there are mass arrests, select this.
- **Government police - assumed** - The police department is not named but any of the following apply:

- the protest occurs entirely off campus
- the protest causes considerable disruption off campus, e.g. blocking traffic on an entire block
- the police are using paddy wagon, horses, helicopters, motorcycle (vehicles other than cars, SUVs, or bikes)
- the protest is opposing police (e.g., violence, racism) + hundreds of protestors + at least part of protest happens outside a police department
- location is a federal or state/provincial government building, e.g. the Capitol

Do not select if it is clear that university police were involved and the protest happens partially on campus but does not fit the bulleted criteria above and there is no other indication of involvement of government police.

- **Riot police** - Identified as “riot police” and/or as wearing riot gear. If in Canada, also select Government police or Government police - assumed.
- **Secret Service** - Protects the U.S. president and other government leaders
- **Private security** - Employed by a company and/or (contracted) work for a company, e.g., a shopping mall
- **NA/Unclear** - do not select this if you selected any of the other options above. This includes if the protest is on and off campus and the text provides no clues as to which type of police were involved.

Police Actions

These categories capture how police manage protest events. Most categories refer to what police do during the protest, although “Communications” typically happen before or after the protest event. Do not code if the text refers to future planned activities that have not happened yet (e.g., Event 25060). Do not code activities if the police and/or journalist are speculating that they may have happened or may happen, e.g. protestors “were likely given a ticket for not collaborating” #10511. The information on Police Actions might come from the police, the protestors, and/or the journalist through their own observations or their sources, which could include police, protestors, administrators, and others; often it is not clear where the journalist got the information.

For these **Engagement categories** (above the line), do not also select “Monitor/Present” because we assume the police are (or were or will be) present at the protest :

- **Instruct/Warn** - Ask/tell protestors to do something; the protestors may or may not cooperate; e.g. disperse, move the location of their protest, tell protestors they cannot block traffic, ask for ID, verbally negotiate with protestors e.g., on allowable actions. Inform protestors they are in violation of policy or doing something illegal, e.g. trespassing,

unlawfully assembling. May or may not imply there will be negative consequences, e.g. threaten arrests.

- **Constrain:** Proactively physically repressing or restricting protestors' actions (or attempting to do so), in order to compel or force the protestors to follow a different course of action from the one they are trying to take (or might try to take). Typically, stopping protestors who are trying to enter a room or building, e.g. for a meeting, or an intervention into an ongoing march that is becoming unruly or is likely to become unruly. E.g., erecting barricades, encircling or kettling protestors, stopping or redirecting protestors away from going somewhere they are trying to go, a police line blocking a road (#2583/Event 21382). E.g., "The police... accompanied the march on horseback, on bikes, and in riot gear, while closely containing the crowd" #10975/Event 19772). If it is unclear that protestors really are trying to access a space (e.g., University Police would not let student protesters within 50 feet of the Student Union Building #761), code as Monitoring instead.
- **Remove (Individual) Protesters** - One, a few, some but not all, e.g., escorting out
- **End Protest** - If the police do something that causes the protestors to end their protest, e.g. protestors disperse when the police are trying to get them to leave. The police actions might prompt all protestors to leave when they remove the protestors, dismantle an Occupy encampment, or threaten to arrest. "Police presence was heavy throughout the protest, although no arrests were made. After a brief standoff with police, the crowd was dispersed for blocking traffic." #11268 If it is not clear if police actions ended a protest, rely on the Event Description, which will summarize the entire protest event. The text should indicate that the protest ended and that there is reason to believe this was due to the police activities (e.g., 11625 event 18988 does not provide enough information to code as End the Protest but event 17986 does). If the police have removed physical objects important to a protest, bring this for discussion; if a banner that is coded as the protest is taken down by police, code this (#6641).
- **Force: Vague/Body** - Effort by police officers to compel protestors to comply by using their bodies (or text is vague on how the police did this), E.g. pushing protestors. Text should be explicit that force was used.
- **Force: Weapon** - Effort by police officers to compel protestors to comply by using a weapon. Contains specific reference to weapons used, e.g. pepper spray, batons, dogs. A shield can be used as a weapon but that should be clear from the text. Text should be explicit that force was used.
- **Force: 2+ (Multiple) Types of Weapons** - Used Effort by police officers to compel protestors to comply by using multiple types of weapon. Contains specific reference to weapons used, e.g. pepper spray, batons, and dogs. Text should be explicit that force was used.

- **Detain** - Protesters are under police control for some period of time and not arrested (e.g., brought to the station, held in a wagon, brief and cursory holding, “subject to search” [10591] stopped the street for questioning). The protestor detained is not free to leave until the officer decides to.
- **Arrest or Attempted Arrest** - Protesters are arrested (handcuffs or other restraint on movement) and detained (i.e. taken into police custody), or police tried unsuccessfully to arrest a protestor, e.g. the protestor ran away. Do not automatically select “Detain.” Do not select if the text only says “apprehend” and it is not clearly an arrest.
- **Arrests - Large Scale 50+** - Protestors arrested total or the majority of protestors (more than half), can happen over an extended period, e.g. an entire day.
- **Formal Accusation** or Statement that a Formal Accusation Will be Filed - charges, citations, tickets, fine, a specific type of order (e.g., stay-away order), for activities such as obstructing traffic, trespassing, disorderly conduct, violating the University’s Code of Rights and Responsibilities. Do not code if the police only threaten formal accusations contingent on protestors doing something, e.g. ending an occupation on university-owned farmland (#220).
- **Disputed Actions** - Protestors claim police did something to their protest, but the police, administration, and/or journalist deny it or provide a contradictory account, e.g. #2419. Do not select if there could be a dispute but the police refused to comment.
- **Penalized** - Police officer(s) face some kind of sanctions for how they policed campus/higher education protest. This includes a resignation by a police employee (in that case, also select Resign/Fire). Mostly likely to be campus police. E.g., following controversy over the Univ of California- Davis campus police pepper spraying student protestors, the chief of campus police resigned #303. Uncommon.

For the Engagement categories (above the line), do not also select “Monitor & Soft Control”; we assume the police are present (or will be present or were present) at the protest:

- **Monitor/Present** - Minimal engagement and soft control. Police are present at the protest but more “in the background.” They may remain stationary, eg. indicating physical boundaries of an event to keep protestors on the planned route, blocking a traffic lane to make space for a march, guarding an entrance to a building to signal to protestors that they cannot enter. And/or they may be moving, eg. escorting protestors on a planned route, following protestors’ march. Police may give instructions to protestors but should clearly not be warnings or threats, e.g., asking people not to walk on grass, telling protestors which direction the march goes. Common rationales: maintain order, public safety, keep protestors safe from traffic, not impede traffic. “Peaceful Policing.” **If you encounter codings where you think both Monitoring + Instruct apply, flag them for discussion.**

- **Cooperate/Coordinate** - Work with protestors in advance of (or during) a protest to ensure safety. Includes engaging or fulfilling a request from protestors, e.g., Delivering fruit to the university president. This action is uncommon. The cooperation or coordination should be explicitly stated in the text, e.g. the police and the protestors met in advance and planned the route of a march together.
- **Participate** - Participate in protest or otherwise identify with the protestors and/or their cause, e.g., joining a march, hold a candle at a vigil, expressing solidarity/agreement; identify with the protestors and/or their cause, e.g., a police float in a Pride march. This action is uncommon.
- **Breaking the Rules/"Violating Law/P&P'** - Police communicate that protestors are breaking the law or university rules, policies, procedures (eg. 11033 - the rally on the school premises disobeyed noise rules). And/or state that protestors need to abide by the university's procedures and policies for protesting and/or the law, but are not e.g., describe a protest as "unlawful assembly," tell protestors they should have applied for permit, tell protestors to register as a student org. The police might communicate this information directly to protestors as instructions or a warning (in that case,also select Instruct/Warn) or they might communicate it in a different context. Do not select with Detain, Arrest, Arrest-Large Scale, or Formal Accusation (because it's redundant) or with Monitoring. Do not select if only the journalist states that the protest was illegal.
- **NA/Unclear** - e.g., none of the options listed above

Police Presence and Size

Assume one police officer per car.

- **Small.** 1 to 5 officers or described as "small" or "some officers" with no other indication of size. Assume 1 officer per car (although that is not always true).
- **Substantial** - The police presence is larger than 5 officers or any of the following
 - Multiple types of police are involved (e.g., university, state/provincial, and federal- can be Univ or Govt Police- Assumed) or involvement of any riot police (rarely fewer than 5)
 - Large scale arrests (50+, regardless of time period)
 - Protest is outside or inside a federal or state/provincial government building or the city hall of the 10 largest cities (NYC, LA, Chicago, Houston, Phoenix, Philadelphia, San Antonio TX, Toronto, Montreal, Vancouver). E.g. police were in front of and behind the marching protestors and lined the sides of the protest.
 - The massive 2012 and 2015 Montreal student strikes concerning tuition and 2015 Toronto strikes concerning labour

- The size/scale of protest (e.g., hundreds of protestors, “filled the street for many blocks”) **and** at least **one** of the following:
 - the protest is off-campus and causes considerable disruption (e.g., blocking automobile traffic on road(s), a large encampment/occupation)
 - police activities happening at a large scale (e.g., multiple blockades, police monitoring in multiple places)

The purpose of this category is to avoid using “Unclear” when the text gives some clues as to the size

- **Heavily Policed** - Select if either applies:

- There is a high ratio of police to protestors - specifically, the police outnumber protestors (#10975) or are more than half the number of protestors.
- A university administrator or police department representative describes the protest as heavily policed or policed more than is typical, e.g. #5468 “the Chief of Police admitted that such a large protective force was not standard.”

You do not need to select “Substantial.” Select “Small” in the highly unusual situations where a very small protest is heavily policed.

- **Motorized Presence:** Police in two or more types of motorized vehicles such as vans, paddy wagons, a helicopter. Not horses because their uses are still mixed, e.g. crowd control, creating a more casual environment. Not bicycles.

You do not need to select “Substantial.” Select “Small” in the highly unusual situations where a very small protest is heavily policed.

- **NA/Unclear** - e.g. small army of police officers, a public communications statement from a police representative only that does not mention the size of the police presence.

Protestor Resistance to Police Actions

This category captures protestors’ pushback against police activity. Protestors’ resistance tends to be reactive and may be aggressive or could be non-violent. Usually involves physical acts of resistance (rather than verbal statements or signs criticizing police). Examples: ignoring a police declaration that a protest is illegal (i.e. remaining at the protest), refusing to comply with police commands such as an order to disperse, filming the police, running away from attempted arrest, pushing through a police blockade, throwing rocks or mud balls at police cars, getting charged with resisting arrest, going limp during an arrest and then getting carried out by police (Article #4408). There is often resistance when police “Instruct/Warn” and protestors ignore that.

If the text only refers to an “incident,” “confrontation,” “stand-off,” “a struggle,” or similarly vague language but does not provide more detail, code this as “Not relevant.” Such text is not enough to determine if there was resistance. Journalists sometimes use such words vaguely or just to describe a police action such as an intervention or an arrest. If the journalist or opinion writer is critical of the police, that does not mean there necessarily was resistance.

Situations you may encounter that you should raise at a meeting: it is unclear if the person(s) resisting is a protestor, counterprotestor, or observer/bystander. (e.g., #3014 - individual records the police); the resistance is implied or vague *e.g., 888 - police “attempted” to arrest); it’s unclear to you if the event involves some or collective resistance.

- **NA/Unclear** - no resistance reported
- **Yes - Some** - not clearly coordinated by protestors or resisted by one, a few, less than half of the protestors or very vague. Choose this if there was the resistance but the numbers and planning are not clear from the article.
- **Yes - Collective** - resisted by all protestors or by the majority (half or more) protestors and/or was coordinated or planned by protestors. If there is resistance to police but the text is vague as to whether it is “some” or “collective,” code as collective if the protestors also are trying to be very disruptive, e.g. shut down a highway ramp #3220, (continue to) occupy a building or other location when police are present and there are indications the police are trying to end the occupation (e.g., stopping food from reaching occupiers #209). If the form is an occupation/sit-in, there is likely to be collective resistance.